

ENSURING QUALITY AND SAFETY OF LIGHT INDUSTRY PRODUCTS

N.S. Sotvoldiyeva¹, A.K. Sativaldiev²

Assistant Andijan State Technical institute¹

PhD, Associate Professor Andijan State Technical institute²

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Abstract. Ensuring the quality and safety of light industry products is one of the key factors influencing consumer demand and the development of this sector. The article discusses the main aspects, methods, and standards aimed at improving product quality and ensuring safety in the light industry. It analyzes the crucial stages of production, including design, development, testing, and certification of products. Attention is also given to legislative requirements impacting product quality and safety, as well as the application of modern technologies to improve them.

Keywords: experiment, control, method, evaluation, variance analysis, regression, criteria, research, graph, methodology, correlation.

INTRODUCTION. The light industry encompasses the production of clothing, textile goods, footwear, leather products, furniture, and other items aimed at satisfying the needs of the population. Given the highly competitive environment and the many requirements imposed on products, ensuring their quality and safety has become a crucial task for both manufacturers and regulators.

The light industry of Uzbekistan is one of the leading and dynamically developing sectors. It plays a significant role in solving national tasks and addresses vital interests in many regions. It contributes to the harmonious development of regions, ensures employment, and improves the well-being of the population, helping establish and develop small and private businesses.

A key direction for utilizing internal reserves and opportunities has been the gradual increase in the depth of garment processing—571 billion sums (143.4). As part of the localization program, finished products and components worth 566.8 billion sums were produced under 36 projects. [3].

In the context of globalization and fierce competition, the issues of ensuring a high level of quality and product safety are becoming increasingly important. Compliance with international standards and national regulations is the foundation for the successful operation of enterprises producing mass consumption goods.

The main problems facing domestic manufacturers in terms of improving product quality management include:

- Strengthening the mechanism of quality management systems' impact on all stages of the product life cycle;
- Integrating marketing activities into the product quality management system;
- Focusing quality management systems, as well as all production activities, on the consumer.

The modern problems of limited implementation are no longer methodological but are purely practical, caused by a lack of qualified personnel, especially in marketing, limited organizational-technical and material bases of enterprises, insufficient experience in the mass

application of statistical methods, delays in automation, and digitalization of technological and managerial processes. [1].

METHODOLOGY. An important aspect in finding ways to improve market protection mechanisms for light industry products in Russia is studying international experience—as an example of implementing various measures and tools to ensure the competitiveness of domestic production and protect national interests.

Thus, Uzbekistan, one of the key economic powers in the Central Asian region, is actively developing its own light industry. Corresponding measures have been adopted to protect the market from illegal imports, aimed at supporting domestic production. The country has introduced customs duties on imported clothing and textiles to reduce competition from foreign manufacturers. In addition, state financial support programs for local entrepreneurs, such as preferential loans and subsidies for light industry development, are in place. [4].

Uzbekistan adopted the Cabinet of Ministers' Resolution No. 556 of 30.09.2022, "On measures to further expand deep processing and the production of finished goods with high added value in textile and sewing-knitting enterprises, as well as financial support for their export," establishing procedures for subsidy allocation for the period from February 1, 2022, to January 1, 2025. According to the introduced rules, enterprises implementing projects for the production of dyed fabric, blended and dyed textile products in Karakalpakstan and regional areas are allocated subsidies from the Textile Industry Support Fund under the Export Promotion Agency, covering 10% of the equipment cost, up to \$500,000 equivalent. The resolution also includes further stimulation of investment projects aimed at producing finished textile products with high added value.

Main Requirements for the Quality of Light Industry Products. The quality of light industry products is determined by many factors, including the reliability of materials, the accuracy of technological processes, durability, aesthetic characteristics, and consumer expectations. Product quality evaluation usually includes the following criteria:

- Functionality— the ability of the product to perform its core tasks.
- Performance characteristics – strength, wear resistance, and resistance to external influences.
- Aesthetics— appearance, design, and comfort in use.

- Environmental friendliness – the use of materials that are safe for the environment and health.

To ensure high product quality in the light industry, it is essential to have a control system at all stages of product creation: from concept and design development to serial production and market supply.

METHODS OF ENSURING PRODUCT QUALITY

Various methods are used to control the quality of light industry products, including:

-Quality at each stage of the production process. To achieve this, quality management systems such as ISO 9001 are implemented in enterprises, ensuring control at all stages—from design and development to mass production and delivery of finished products.

- Safety and quality standards. The application of international and national standards (e.g., GOST, ISO, ASTM) plays a key role in ensuring product compliance with established requirements.

- Testing and certification. Various laboratory tests are conducted to check product quality and safety, including determining the physical and chemical characteristics of materials used in products and their compliance with sanitary norms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. ENSURING SAFETY OF LIGHT INDUSTRY PRODUCTS. Light industry products must comply with a range of standards that ensure their safety for the health and life of consumers. It is particularly important to meet safety requirements in the production of children's clothing, footwear, and textiles, as these products most frequently come into contact with the skin and may cause allergic reactions or other adverse effects.

The main aspects to consider when ensuring product safety include:

-*Material safety. The use of only certified fabrics, dyes, adhesives, and other materials that have passed safety tests for health.

- Technological processes. Manufacturing processes should exclude the use of hazardous chemicals, such as carcinogenic or toxic components, and minimize their emissions into the environment.

- Certification and compliance with safety standards. In Russia and other countries, there are a number of mandatory and voluntary certificates confirming product safety (e.g., GOST R certificate or CE mark in Europe).

LEGISLATIVE AND REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS Legislation in the light industry sector imposes strict requirements on the quality and safety of products. In Russia, the most important documents are:

- Technical Regulations of the Customs Union (TR TS) – mandatory safety requirements for products, including textiles, clothing, and footwear.
- GOSTs and standards– regulations governing the production of light industry products, including material quality, product standards, and control over compliance with these standards.
- Sanitary and environmental regulations – ensuring product safety in terms of health and environmental protection.

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR ENSURING QUALITY AND SAFETY. Modern quality management recognizes that quality management cannot be effective after the production process is completed. It is also essential to ensure quality before the production process. Quality is determined by the actions of many random, local, and subjective factors. To prevent these factors from affecting quality, an effective quality management system is necessary. This requires a comprehensive set of measures for continuous impact on the product creation process to maintain an appropriate level of quality.

In recent years, new technologies have been actively introduced in the light industry, which contribute to the improvement of product quality and safety. These include:

- The use of nanotechnology in fabric production, allowing the creation of stronger and more durable materials.
- 3D printing– enabling the creation of unique, high-quality products with minimal costs.
- Automated control systems – implementing automatic systems for monitoring and controlling product quality at all stages of production.
- Ecological technologies– using safe and environmentally friendly materials, reducing environmental impact, and minimizing production waste.

CONCLUSION. Ensuring the quality and safety of light industry products is essential for meeting consumer needs and maintaining market competitiveness. Achieving high quality standards requires attention to all aspects—from material selection and technology to compliance with regulatory and legislative requirements. Implementing modern technologies and certifying products helps ensure the reliability and safety of goods, contributing to the sustainable development of the industry.

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